

PROPOSITION FOR A PRE-SUBMISSION INQUIRY:

**STREAMING RAMADAN IN TIMES OF PANDEMIC
METHODS AND ETHICS OF A (N)ETHNOGRAPHY OF HYBRID ISLAMIST
ACTIVISM**

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Abstract

Due to the worldwide restrictions caused by the Coronavirus pandemic of 2020-2021, the most important Muslim holiday of the year, Ramadan, did not take place in the usual way. The Islamic month of fasting, which also includes communal prayers and social gatherings, was transformed into virtual meetings. Through ethnographic research on Islamist activism in contemporary Morocco conducted between 2016 and 2020, the purpose of this study is to reflect on the main challenges and changes posed by the Coronavirus pandemic to both the researcher and the social actors involved, as well as the methods and ethics of ethnographic research online. Starting from the case study of the activities of political Islam youth groups, both inside and outside the Internet, this article aims to argue for a multimodal and interdisciplinary methodology as an approach that must extend beyond this period of uncertainty and precarity.

Introduction

The onset of the Coronavirus pandemic in 2020 disrupted every facet of life worldwide, challenging social norms, rituals, and practices that had been deeply ingrained in societies for centuries. For the Muslim world, one of the most significant disruptions was the observance of Ramadan, a holy month of fasting, prayer, and communal gatherings. The usual bustling streets, vibrant marketplaces, and the sounds of the call to prayer gave way to a quieter, more isolated Ramadan, as virtual meetings replaced physical interactions. In Morocco, where Islam plays a central role in daily life, this transformation was particularly profound. This article takes an ethnographic journey into the evolving landscape of Islamic activism in contemporary Morocco, exploring how the COVID-19 pandemic affected this space.

Drawing on ethnographic research conducted between 2016 and 2020, this study reflects on the challenges and changes brought about by the pandemic to both the social actors involved in Islamic activism and the methods and ethics of conducting ethnographic research in the digital age. By focusing on the activities of political Islam youth groups, both inside and outside the Internet, we aim to demonstrate the need for a multimodal and interdisciplinary approach, which extends beyond this period of uncertainty and precarity.

I. Ramadan in Morocco: A Paradigm Shift

The Coronavirus pandemic disrupted not only the everyday lives of Moroccans but also the deeply spiritual and communal essence of Ramadan. Traditionally, this holy month sees mosques filled with worshipers, families coming together for iftar meals, and social interactions that reinforce the sense of unity and devotion. However, in 2020 and 2021, with restrictions in place, Moroccans had to adapt to a new reality. Virtual meetings and online sermons replaced physical gatherings, challenging the conventional way of celebrating Ramadan. For Islamic activists and youth groups in Morocco, this was a moment of adaptation and transformation.

II. Ethnographic Research in the Digital Age

The constraints of the COVID-19 pandemic forced ethnographers to rethink their methodologies. Traditional ethnographic research, which heavily relies on physical presence and immersive engagement with the subjects of study, had to evolve. The digital space emerged as a significant avenue for continuing research while adhering to safety guidelines. In the case of Morocco, this shift meant that ethnographers had to explore the digital domains of Islamic activism and understand the evolving dynamics of online engagement.

III. Political Islam Youth Groups: A Case Study

Political Islam youth groups in Morocco have long played a pivotal role in shaping the country's sociopolitical landscape. However, the pandemic altered their strategies and tactics. Instead of relying solely on physical rallies and gatherings, they turned to online platforms to maintain their connections and influence. Virtual meetings, webinars, and social media became crucial tools for disseminating their messages, enabling them to engage with a broader audience and adapt to the new realities of the pandemic.

IV. (N)Ethnography : A Multimodal and Interdisciplinary Approach

The experience of conducting ethnographic research during the pandemic underscores the necessity of adopting a multimodal and interdisciplinary methodology. To truly understand the shifting dynamics of Islamic activism in Morocco, researchers need to integrate both physical and digital realms into their investigations. This approach allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how the pandemic has impacted the social actors and their engagement strategies.

By drawing from diverse disciplines, such as anthropology, sociology, and digital humanities, researchers can explore the multifaceted dimensions of Islamic activism. The virtual space cannot be viewed in isolation; it must be considered in conjunction with the traditional aspects of religious and political engagement to grasp the holistic picture.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic brought forth an unprecedented challenge to Islamic activism in Morocco, transforming the way Ramadan is observed and the methods of conducting ethnographic research. As the world gradually emerges from the uncertainties of the pandemic, it is essential to recognize the enduring impact of this period on social actors and research methodologies. A multimodal and interdisciplinary approach that bridges the physical and digital worlds is crucial for comprehending the intricate dynamics of contemporary Islamic activism and adapting to an ever-evolving landscape. This approach will be invaluable not only during periods of precarity but also in understanding the future trajectory of social movements in a digital age.